

Influence of genetic and interannual factors on the fatty acids profile of virgin olive oil

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Virgin olive oil

Monounsaturated fatty acids

Polyunsaturated fatty acids

Saturated fatty acids

Cultivar

Climate conditions

ABSTRACT

Among olive oil nutritional benefits, it is worth mentioning its fatty acids composition with predominance of monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFAs). We have evaluated the influence of the cultivar and interannual factors on the fatty acids profile of virgin olive oil samples obtained from 45 and 71 cultivars along three and two consecutive crop seasons, respectively. The cultivars were classified in two groups according to the fatty acids composition: (1) high content in MUFAs and moderate content in saturated and polyunsaturated fatty acids (SFAs and PUFAs, respectively) and (2) moderate content in MUFAs and high content in SFAs/PUFAs. We also observed variations in the fatty acids content with the climate conditions, which can significantly alter the saturated and unsaturated profiles. Thus, a significant decrease in MUFAs and an increase in SFAs/PUFAs concentrations was found when the precipitation accumulated within the June-October period was reduced.

1. Introduction

Olive oil (OO) represents the main source of fat in the Mediterranean diet, which is characterized by a high intake of cereals, vegetables, legumes, nuts and fruits (Willett et al., 1995). Many studies have associated the Mediterranean diet with the prevention of cardiovascular diseases and some types of cancer, atherosclerosis, diabetes and obesity (Farràs et al., 2021). Recently, the Mediterranean diet has revealed a higher potential for secondary prevention of major cardiovascular events than a low-fat diet (Delgado-Lista et al., 2022). Also, the PRE-DIMED study showed a reduction of cardiovascular events in patients subjected to a Mediterranean diet supplemented with extra virgin olive oil and nuts versus a reduced-fat diet (Estruch et al., 2018).

The health value of OO has been mainly attributed to a balanced composition between minor and major compounds (Rallo et al., 2018). Minor components, represented by phenols, phytosterols and tocopherols, among others, make of OO a nutraceutical food product with unique health benefits (Gavahian et al., 2019; Jones & AbuMweis, 2009). This minor fraction is present almost exclusively in virgin olive oil (VOO) since most of these compounds are removed in the refining

treatments (Bouaziz, Feki, Ayadi, Jemai, & Sayadi, 2010). Healthy properties of the major fraction of OO are ascribed to the abundance of monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFAs), being oleic acid the predominant fatty acid (55–83% of the total fatty acids content). This profile contributes to the reduction of cholesterol levels and to the risk of cardiovascular diseases (Pérez-Jiménez, Ruano, Perez-Martinez, Lopez-Segura, & Lopez-Miranda, 2007).

The MUFAs profile also contributes to the oxidative stability of OO, which is significantly explained by the oleic acid/linoleic acid (MUFAs/polyunsaturated fatty acids or PUFAs) ratio. Recently, the oleic acid/linoleic acid ratio has been studied from the point of view of the diverse enzymatic reactions involved in the biosynthesis of fatty acids for genetic improvement of OO quality (Ben Ayed et al., 2022; Hernández, Sicardo, Belaj, & Martínez-Rivas, 2021). This study concluded that *OeFAD2-2* and *OeFAD2-5* genes and the different specificities of extraplastidial acyltransferase enzymes are responsible for the variability of the oleic acid/linoleic acid ratio in OO from different olive cultivars.

León et al. (2008) evaluated the fatty acid composition of OO from fifteen advanced olive selections obtained by crossbreeding and their

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2023.136175>

Received 28 November 2022; Received in revised form 13 April 2023; Accepted 13 April 2023

Available online 18 April 2023

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genitors ('Arbequina', 'Frantoio' and 'Picual') for three consecutive harvest seasons. They reported a strong genetic effect and significant differences between genotypes for every fatty acid and ratio evaluated. The authors indicated that an efficient selection based on fatty acid composition can be achieved by considering a single year of evaluation at the seedling stage (León, De la Rosa, Gracia, Barranco, & Rallo, 2008). Rondani et al. (2011) characterized the fatty acids profile in OO from seventeen cultivars to study the influence of the cultivar factor on the oleic acid variability. They suggested an effect of genotype \times environment interaction in the variability of oleic acid content for some cultivars (Rondanini, Castro, Searles, & Rousseaux, 2011).

The fatty acid composition of OO is affected by many other factors. Among them, the ripening of the olives reported an influence on the variability of this profile in Nizip Yaglik OOs based on three maturity periods (Amanpour, Kelebek, & Selli, 2019). Regarding the climatic parameters, the growing area conditions, rainfalls or temperature during the oil accumulation phase influence the content of fatty acids (García-Inza, Castro, Hall, & Rousseaux, 2014; Issaoui et al., 2010; Rizwan et al., 2019).

Despite these characterization studies, few of them have involved a representative number of cultivars. For this reason, we planned to characterize the fatty acids profile of VOO samples obtained from 45 cultivars over three consecutive crop seasons. The purposes of this research were: (i) to study the influence of the cultivar and interannual factors in the variability of the fatty acids profile; (ii) to find clusters of cultivars according to variability trends in the fatty acids profile; and (iii) to evaluate the effect of climatic parameters (accumulated precipitation and mean temperature) in the period June–October, the critical period for fruits development.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples

VOO samples were obtained in the frame of a previous study targeted at evaluating the cultivar effect on the phenolic profile (Miho et al., 2021). Olive fruits were harvested from the World Olive Germplasm Bank in Cordoba (WOGB) (CAP-UCO-IFAPA), specifically in the collection located in the University of Cordoba (Cordoba, Spain, 37°55'56.5" N, 4°43'13.3" W and 173 m a.s.l.). Harvesting seasons were 2015, 2016 and 2017.

The climate of the WOGB area is typically Mediterranean. The total rainfalls in 2015, 2016, and 2017 were 352.1, 735.2, and 463.5 mm, respectively. The three years presented similar average temperatures (28 °C) with the maximum values during July and August. On the contrary, the months with the lowest temperature were December and January, with mean temperatures close to 10 °C (www.juntadeandalucia.es). The collection was irrigated from May to September, applying 100 m³ of water per ha per week (2000 m³ of water per year) using drip irrigation. Foliar fertilization (2% potassium nitrate) was applied four times per year in November, March, May, and September.

Olive fruit samples (2 kg) were manually harvested from each tree by sampling all orientations within the canopy. The olives were sampled from October to December when the fruits were at a ripening index (RI) 2.0 (yellowish-red color) according to the method proposed by the International Olive Council (IOC, 2020) to standardize the conditions. With this strategy, 70% of the cultivars were harvested in October, 25% in November and 5% in December. VOO samples were extracted by an Abencor equipment (MC2 Ingeniería y Sistemas, Sevilla, Spain) under optimized conditions: malaxation time, 30 min; malaxation temperature, 28 °C; centrifugation speed, 3500 rpm (Peres, Martins, & Ferreira-Dias, 2014). No water was added at any step of the process to minimize losses of phenolic compounds. A total of 45 cultivars, two olive trees per cultivar, were sampled for three seasons (45 cultivars \times 2 trees \times 3 years, 270 samples), while the study was extended to 71 cultivars at two seasons (71 \times 2 trees \times 2 years, 284 samples).

2.2. Fatty acids profiling analysis

The fatty acids profile was obtained by a gas chromatograph coupled to flame ionization detector (GC–FID) by application of a modified version of the reference IOC method developed by Tomé-Rodríguez et al. (Tomé-Rodríguez, Ledesma-Escobar, Penco-Valenzuela & Priego-Capote, 2021). An aliquot of 0.05 g from each OO sample was vortexed with 1 mL of 0.5 N methanolic potassium hydroxide at 30 °C for 10 min for transesterification. Then, 1 mL of *n*-hexane was added and shaken for 5 min to obtain a biphasic system. The hexane phase containing the fatty acids methyl esters (FAMES) was collected and 1/25 (v/v) diluted prior to injecting 1 μ L into the GC–FID.

Separation of FAMES was carried out using a 7820A GC (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with an autosampler, a split/splitless injector, and coupled to a FID. An SP™-2560 fused silica capillary column (100 mm \times 0.25 mm I.D., 0.2 μ m film thickness, Agilent) provided by Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA) was used as analytical column. The GC–FID analysis was performed according to the following conditions: injector temperature, 250 °C; injection in splitless mode; gas flow, 1.0 mL min⁻¹. The oven temperature was programmed as follows: initial temperature 100 °C (hold for 5 min), increased at 4 °C min⁻¹ to 240 °C (hold for 20 min), and finally 10 °C min⁻¹ to 250 °C (hold for 4 min). Total analysis time was 65 min, with 10 min added for re-establishing and equilibrating the initial conditions. Identification was carried out by comparison of the peak retention time with those obtained from the analysis of a FAMES multistandard from Sigma-Aldrich (Supelco 37 component FAME mix).

2.3. Determination of oil extraction yield and fruit moisture

Oil extraction yield and fruit moisture were determined by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) in an accredited laboratory ("CM EUROPA S.L.", Martos, Spain). An NMR spectrometer, NMS110C/125/40 RTA model, from Bruker (Rheinstetten, Germany) equipped with a permanent magnet of 0.237 Tesla and an operating frequency of 10 Mhz for 1H was used. The system included a temperature control unit that was set at 40 °C with a precision of \pm 0.3 °C and a stability of 0.01 °C.

Sample tubes with a capacity for 40–50 g were used for analysis. Measurements were performed by radiofrequency pulses at 10 MHz and 1 s/pulse for 5 s.

The protocol was carried out with 25 g of ground olive fruit that was deposited on a thermo-resistant film and introduced into a forced air convection drying oven at 103 °C for 12 h. Then, the paste was cooled for 30 min and weighed after drying. NMR measurements were based on: (i) selection of the olive calibration curve; (ii) indication of the wet weight of the sample; and (iii) introduction of the dried sample into the measuring tube for analysis in the NMR equipment.

2.4. Data treatment and statistical analysis

Quantitation was carried out by integrating the peak area for each considered fatty acid by Qualitative Analysis software (version 10.0, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The content of each fatty acid was expressed as percentage of the total peak area considering all fatty acids. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to evaluate the effect of the two variables (cultivar and crop season) as well as the interaction of them on the fatty acids content. A pairwise comparison (Tukey HSD, $p \leq 0.05$) was used to analyze differences in fatty acids considering the influence of the genotype and crop season. Data were previously normalized by Box-Cox transformation and distribution was checked by the Shapiro-Wilk and Levene tests.

Three multivariate analyses were carried out to classify the cultivars into clusters according to their fatty acids profile. First, Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) was performed to find discrimination patterns in VOO samples. Dissimilarity was estimated by Euclidean distance, agglomeration was based on the Ward method, and the Hartigan index

was used for truncation. In parallel, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was also applied to find distribution patterns of cultivars in a two-dimensional plot using the sum of SFAs, MUFAs and PUFAs as variables. Discriminant Analysis (DA) was carried out to confirm the stability of the clusters along the three seasons. Classes weight correction was applied to the total set of samples.

Pearson correlation analysis was also tested in the total set of samples (71 cultivars) to confirm and demonstrate the interaction between the groups of fatty acids: SFAs, MUFAs and PUFAs. Addinsoft (2022), XLSTAT statistical and data analysis solution (<https://www.xlstat.com>) were used for statistical analysis in this research.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of the fatty acids profile in virgin olive oil

The fatty acids composition of VOOs from 45 cultivars at three consecutive crop seasons is shown in [Table 1](#) and [Table S1](#). We observed a high variability in the relative content of C16:0, C18:1 and C18:2, the three most abundant fatty acids, with ranges of 8.77–24.23%, 45.00–80.69%, and 2.07–26.86%, respectively. Previously, other authors have reported similar variability ranges for main fatty acids as those obtained by [Rondanini et al. \(2011\)](#) for C16:0 (12.99–19.2%), C18:1 (51.8–71.9%), and C18:2 (7.7–22.9%) and by [León et al. \(2008\)](#) for C16:0 (12.07–18.38%), C18:1 (61.15–78.26%), and C18:2 (2.00–15.37%). On the other hand, C14:0, C17:0, C22:0 and C24:0 reported the lowest contents, with mean values below 0.1%. Considering the average of the three crop seasons, the highest relative concentration of C18:1 was achieved by Mastoidis and Morona with 77.15 and 76.27%, respectively, whereas the lowest levels were provided by Blanqueta and Picudo with 55.19 and 57.12%, respectively. For C18:2, Blanqueta and Picudo reported the highest relative content with 20.74 and 18.74%, respectively, while Cornicabra and Manzanilla Prieta (both with C18:1 above 75%) gave the lowest contents with 3.82 and 5.31%, respectively. Finally, Gordal de Granada and Blanqueta were the top cultivars in terms of C16:0 relative concentration, 19.25 and 18.54%, respectively, while Picual de Almería and Mastoidis were on the opposite side, with 11.70 and 11.93%, respectively ([Table 1](#)).

We measured the interannual variation for the studied fatty acids in the 45 cultivars set analyzed in the tree crop seasons. Concerning the main fatty acids, ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’, ‘Gordal de Granada’, ‘Loaime’, ‘Royal de Cazorla’, ‘Blanqueta’ and ‘Gemlik’ showed high variability for C18:1, with standard deviations (SD) higher than 7.0%. Some of these cultivars, such as ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’, ‘Gordal de Granada’, ‘Royal de Cazorla’, ‘Loaime’ and ‘Blanqueta’, also presented a wide variation in the content of C18:2. On the other hand, ‘Gordal de Granada’, ‘Coratina’, ‘Alfajara’, ‘Alameño de Montilla’, ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’ and ‘Blanqueta’ reported high variability in C16:0 content, with SD higher than 2.3%. On the opposite side, the lowest variation (SD < 2.0%) for C18:1 occurred for ‘Mollar de Cieza’, ‘Mastoidis’, ‘Joanenca’, ‘Ulliri i Bardhe i Tiranes’, ‘Caballo’ and ‘Abou Choki’; for C18:2 the cultivars with lowest variability (SD < 0.90%) were ‘Cornicabra’, ‘Mastoidis’, ‘Plementa Bjelica’, ‘Arbequina’, ‘Arbosana’ and ‘Joanenca’; and for C16:0 ‘Abou Choki’, ‘Mastoidis’, ‘Koroneiki’, ‘Negrillo de la Carlota’ and ‘Morona’ SD values below 0.70% were reported. These results revealed that some cultivars experienced a higher interannual variability in the fatty acids profile represented by the most concentrated compounds, C16:0, C18:1 and C18:2, whereas other cultivars were characterized by a reduced variability in the selected period ([Fig. 1](#)). This cultivar effect should be considered in terms of VOO quality and oxidative stability.

Generally, the content of most fatty acids was within the established limits by the International Olive Council (IOC, 2019), except for few cultivars that presented some values outside these required limits at the third agronomic season, particularly for the three most abundant fatty acids C18:1 (<55%), C18:3 (>1.0%) or C18:2 (>21%). With these premises, ‘Blanqueta’ and ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’ gave moderate C18:1

content (45% and 51%, respectively), and high content of C18:2 (27% and 25%) in the third crop season ([Table S1](#)).

Moreover, we evaluated the VOO samples based on nutrition and health claims included in the Regulation (EC) No 1924/2006, lastly amended by Regulation (EU) No 116/2010. In this case, all samples satisfied the requirements according to the fatty acids profile for two nutritional and health claims: high monounsaturated fats content (>45%) and high content of unsaturated fats (>70%). Thus, the top-5 cultivars with the highest content in MUFAs were Mastoidis, Morona, Cornicabra, Manzanilla Prieta and Picual with values above 77%; complementary, the cultivars with the highest content in unsaturated fats were Mastoidis, Coratina, Farga, Cerezuela, Kalamon and Morona, with values above 84.40%.

3.2. Variability in the fatty acids profile of VOO

We applied an ANOVA test followed by the Tukey HSD test to study the VOO fatty acids concentration and the influence of the two main factors involved in this study: cultivar and crop season, as well as the interaction effect ([Fig. 2](#)). The main factor explaining the fatty acids variability was the genotype (cultivar) factor, between 77% and 32% respectively for C18:0 and C14:0. This factor contributed to explain 62.1 and 53.5% of the variability in the content of PUFAs and MUFAs, respectively, and 49.1% for SFAs.

The crop season factor contributed to explain from 4% of the variability for C18:0 to 18% for SFAs. The percentage of variability in MUFAs and PUFAs content associated to the crop season was below 12.5%. On the other hand, the cultivar × crop season (interaction factor) contributed significantly to the variance. Specifically, the interaction factor explained from 13.2% to 37.6% of the variability for C18:0 and C20:1, with a mean contribution around 25% ([Fig. 2](#)).

These results point out the high contribution of the genotype in the olive oil composition of fatty acids and its relative stability in three crop seasons, which agrees with the study reported by [León et al. \(2008\)](#) that considered three genitor cultivars (‘Arbequina’, ‘Frantoio’ and ‘Picual’) and fifteen new genotypes obtained by crossbreeding. Similarly, the authors reported that the variability in the fatty acids profile explained by the genetic factor was between 50 and 90%. Therefore, we conclude that the cultivar is the factor explaining the highest variability in the content of PUFAs and MUFAs. This influence can be ascribed to the mechanism of formation of fatty acids in plants. Fatty acid synthase (FAS) regulates the formation of saturated C16 or C18 acyls. However, unsaturated fatty acids are predominant in most vegetable oils. The formation of C18:1 takes place by desaturation of C18:0 acyl in plastids, being oleate the main product found in these organelles. Complementary, C18:2 synthesis in vegetable tissues mainly occurs outside the plastids ([Ben Ayed et al., 2022](#); [Hernández et al., 2021](#)). Therefore, the enzymatic machinery that governs these conversions is highly influenced by the genotype factor. This is of particular interest since fatty acids and phenolic compounds are responsible for the health effects of olive oil and the oxidative stability ([Miho et al., 2021](#)).

To further understand the classification of the cultivars by the fatty acids profile measured in VOO, three statistical multivariate analyses were carried out. Firstly, Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) was carried out to generate a cluster dendrogram of the cultivars ([Fig. 3A](#)); then, in parallel, a two-dimensional PCA biplot ([Fig. 3B](#)) was carried out to examine the distribution of the cultivars (scores) and the contents of MUFAs, PUFAs and SFAs (loadings). For these two analyses, we used the mean concentrations of fatty acids measured in VOO samples from the extended set (71 cultivars) in two consecutive crop seasons ([Table S2](#)). The cultivars were clustered in two groups as follows: G1 group, cultivars providing VOO with high concentration of MUFAs (>70%) and moderate content in SFAs and PUFAs; and G2 group, cultivars providing VOOs moderately concentrated in MUFAs (<70%) and high content in SFAs and PUFAs ([Table S3](#)). The definition of these two groups agreed with the Pearson correlation analysis carried out for the extended

Table 1
Mean relative concentrations (%) of fatty acids in VOO samples obtained from 45 cultivars in the three crop seasons. Lowercase letters indicate significant differences for each relative concentrations among cultivars ($p < 0.05$).

Cultivar	C14:0	C16:0	C16:1	C17:0	C17:1	C18:0	C18:1	C18:2	C18:3	C20:0	C20:1	C22:0	C24:0	SFAs	MUFAs	PUFAs
Abou Choki	0.02 ^{a-d}	17.62 ^{a-e}	1.75 ^{a-f}	0.04 ^{i-o}	0.09 ^{g-j}	1.83 ^{m-t}	64.46 ^{h-l}	12.54 ^{bj}	1.01 ^{c-k}	0.30 ^{h-m}	0.20 ^{bj}	0.09 ^{d-l}	0.05 ^{b-f}	19.95 ^{a-d}	66.50 ^{f-k}	13.55 ^{a-j}
Alameño de Montilla	0.03 ^{a-b}	14.04 ^{f-o}	1.28 ^{d-l}	0.06 ^{g-n}	0.08 ^{g-j}	2.58 ^{c-j}	70.20 ^{bj}	9.56 ^{g-l}	1.34 ^{a-b}	0.44 ^{b-f}	0.22 ^{a-g}	0.10 ^{b-i}	0.07 ^{a-c}	17.31 ^{b-i}	71.79 ^{b-i}	10.90 ^{f-m}
Aljafara	0.02 ^{a-d}	16.9 ^{a-i}	1.75 ^{a-f}	0.10 ^{a-j}	0.27 ^{a-b}	1.63 ^{r-t}	65.84 ^{e-l}	11.94 ^{bj}	0.87 ^{d-l}	0.33 ^{d-l}	0.21 ^{a-i}	0.08 ^{e-m}	0.05 ^{a-f}	19.11 ^{a-g}	68.08 ^{e-k}	12.81 ^{b-j}
Arbequina	0.02 ^{a-d}	16.24 ^{a-k}	1.68 ^{a-g}	0.10 ^{a-i}	0.19 ^{b-e}	1.97 ^{l-t}	66.52 ^{e-l}	11.87 ^{bj}	0.69 ^{j-n}	0.35 ^{c-k}	0.22 ^{a-i}	0.09 ^{d-l}	0.05 ^{b-f}	18.83 ^{a-g}	68.61 ^{d-k}	12.56 ^{b-j}
Arbosana	0.02 ^{a-d}	15.28 ^{a-m}	1.72 ^{a-g}	0.15 ^{a-c}	0.29 ^{a-b}	1.93 ^{l-t}	70.78 ^{aj}	8.41 ^{h-m}	0.73 ^{g-n}	0.33 ^{e-l}	0.21 ^{b-j}	0.11 ^{a-d}	0.05 ^{b-f}	17.87 ^{a-i}	72.99 ^{a-h}	9.13 ^{h-n}
Blanqueta	0.02 ^{a-d}	18.54 ^{a-c}	1.82 ^{a-f}	0.13 ^{a-f}	0.23 ^{a-c}	1.80 ^{o-t}	55.19 ^j	20.74 ^a	0.81 ^{d-l}	0.38 ^{b-k}	0.20 ^{bj}	0.10 ^{c-j}	0.05 ^{b-f}	21.01 ^{a-b}	57.44 ^k	21.55 ^a
Caballo	0.03 ^{a-d}	13.74 ^{h-o}	0.75 ^{k-o}	0.20 ^a	0.30 ^{a-b}	3.38 ^{a-b}	68.1 ^{c-k}	11.78 ^{bj}	0.89 ^{c-k}	0.45 ^{a-d}	0.22 ^{a-g}	0.10 ^{a-i}	0.06 ^{a-e}	17.96 ^{a-i}	69.37 ^{c-k}	12.67 ^{b-j}
Cerezuela	0.02 ^{a-d}	12.21 ^{m-o}	0.54 ^{n-o}	0.15 ^{a-d}	0.24 ^{a-c}	2.44 ^{d-l}	74.04 ^{a-f}	8.95 ^{h-l}	0.29 ^{d-l}	0.21 ^{j-m}	0.81 ^{a-i}	0.06 ^{k-m}	0.03 ^{e-f}	15.21 ^{h-i}	75.03 ^{a-f}	9.76 ^{h-m}
Chetoui	0.02 ^{a-d}	12.79 ^{k-o}	0.40 ^o	0.06 ^{g-n}	0.06 ^{g-j}	2.39 ^{d-l}	64.02 ^{h-l}	18.74 ^{a-c}	0.74 ^{f-m}	0.38 ^{b-k}	0.27 ^{a-d}	0.09 ^{d-l}	0.04 ^{e-f}	15.75 ^{f-i}	64.76 ^{g-k}	19.48 ^{a-c}
Coratina	0.01 ^{d-d}	12.29 ^{m-o}	0.63 ^{m-o}	0.03 ^{k-o}	0.07 ^{g-j}	2.07 ^{h-r}	66.69 ^{c-l}	9.71 ^{h-l}	0.73 ^{h-n}	0.27 ^{k-m}	0.18 ^{e-j}	0.06 ^{l-m}	0.04 ^{e-f}	14.70 ^j	67.56 ^{h-k}	10.45 ^{g-m}
Cornicabra	0.02 ^{a-d}	14.11 ^{d-o}	1.43 ^{j-o}	0.05 ^{h-o}	0.08 ^{g-j}	3.01 ^{b-f}	75.75 ^{a-d}	3.82 ^{n-o}	0.84 ^{d-l}	0.48 ^{a-b}	0.21 ^{h-h}	0.13 ^{a-c}	0.07 ^{a-b}	17.87 ^{a-i}	77.47 ^{a-c}	4.66 ^{n-o}
Empeltre	0.02 ^{a-d}	16.86 ^{a-g}	1.65 ^{a-h}	0.09 ^{a-f}	0.18 ^{a-c}	2.10 ^{n-t}	66.55 ^{e-l}	10.72 ^{a-h}	1.04 ^{a-e}	0.38 ^{c-k}	0.24 ^{a-e}	0.10 ^{d-l}	0.06 ^{a-c}	19.62 ^{a-d}	68.62 ^{e-k}	11.76 ^{a-h}
Farga	0.02 ^{a-d}	13.11 ^{j-o}	1.20 ^{e-m}	0.03 ^{m-o}	0.06 ^j	1.90 ^{l-t}	71.75 ^{a-i}	10.48 ^{e-k}	0.74 ^{h-n}	0.34 ^{d-l}	0.23 ^{a-g}	0.10 ^{a-i}	0.05 ^{a-f}	15.55 ^{g-i}	73.24 ^{a-h}	11.21 ^{e-m}
Frantoio	0.02 ^{a-d}	15.5 ^{a-l}	1.31 ^{d-k}	0.07 ^{g-n}	0.12 ^{e-i}	2.24 ^{g-p}	68.52 ^{c-j}	10.67 ^{d-k}	0.79 ^{e-m}	0.39 ^{b-j}	0.24 ^{a-g}	0.10 ^{c-j}	0.05 ^{a-f}	18.36 ^{a-h}	70.18 ^{c-j}	11.46 ^{d-m}
Gemlik	0.02 ^{a-d}	16.16 ^{a-k}	1.86 ^{a-e}	0.11 ^{a-g}	0.19 ^{b-e}	2.73 ^{e-m}	66.56 ^{e-l}	10.79 ^{f-l}	0.84 ^{d-l}	0.39 ^{b-j}	0.20 ^{bj}	0.08 ^{d-l}	0.05 ^{a-e}	19.55 ^{a-f}	68.81 ^{c-j}	11.63 ^{f-m}
Gordal de Granada	0.03 ^{a-d}	19.25 ^a	1.66 ^{a-g}	0.08 ^{b-l}	0.10 ^{e-i}	2.37 ^{e-m}	60.80 ^l	18.54 ^{a-e}	0.98 ^{a-i}	0.41 ^{b-i}	0.19 ^{b-j}	0.09 ^{d-l}	0.05 ^{a-f}	22.28 ^a	62.75 ^{h-k}	19.53 ^{a-e}
Hojiblanca	0.03 ^{a-b}	13.11 ^{j-o}	0.85 ^{l-o}	0.15 ^{a-c}	0.26 ^{a-b}	2.59 ^{b-h}	71.84 ^{a-h}	9.39 ^l	1.02 ^{a-g}	0.38 ^{b-k}	0.23 ^{a-g}	0.10 ^{c-j}	0.06 ^{a-e}	16.41 ^{c-i}	73.18 ^{a-g}	10.41 ^{g-m}
Jabaluna	0.03 ^{a-c}	15.28 ^{a-m}	1.52 ^{b-h}	0.06 ^{e-n}	0.09 ^{g-j}	2.54 ^{d-k}	67.09 ^{c-l}	11.66 ^{bj}	0.78 ^{f-m}	0.48 ^{a-b}	0.29 ^{a-b}	0.11 ^{a-e}	0.07 ^{a-b}	18.57 ^{a-h}	68.98 ^{e-k}	12.44 ^{c-j}
Joanenca	0.03 ^{a-b}	18.03 ^{a-c}	2.08 ^{a-c}	0.06 ^{e-n}	0.09 ^{g-j}	2.02 ^{j-s}	65.07 ^{f-l}	10.35 ^{f-l}	1.34 ^{a-c}	0.43 ^{b-e}	0.30 ^{a-c}	0.14 ^a	0.06 ^{a-c}	20.77 ^{a-b}	67.55 ^{f-k}	11.69 ^{d-l}
Kalamon	0.02 ^{a-d}	13.17 ^{j-o}	0.96 ^{b-o}	0.15 ^{a-d}	0.29 ^{a-b}	1.83 ^{p-t}	69.51 ^{b-j}	12.57 ^{bj}	0.84 ^{d-l}	0.31 ^{g-l}	0.24 ^{a-f}	0.08 ^{f-m}	0.04 ^{a-f}	15.6 ⁱ	71.00 ^{b-i}	13.41 ^{b-j}
Koroneiki	0.02 ^{a-d}	13.1 ^o	0.83 ^o	0.05 ^{l-o}	0.11 ^{e-i}	2.15 ^{g-p}	73.58 ^{a-g}	8.62 ^{h-n}	0.84 ^{d-l}	0.36 ^{b-k}	0.21 ^{a-h}	0.10 ^{a-i}	0.05 ^{a-f}	15.81 ^{e-i}	74.73 ^{a-f}	9.46 ^{h-o}
Kotruvsi	0.02 ^{a-d}	14.90 ^{a-n}	1.11 ^{f-m}	0.04 ^{l-o}	0.08 ^{g-j}	2.30 ^{g-o}	63.56 ^{h-l}	16.63 ^{a-f}	0.62 ^{l-n}	0.37 ^{b-k}	0.23 ^{a-g}	0.10 ^{b-j}	0.05 ^{a-f}	17.77 ^{a-i}	64.98 ^{g-k}	17.25 ^{a-f}
Kusha	0.02 ^{a-d}	14.67 ^{b-o}	0.67 ^{l-o}	0.15 ^{a-c}	0.20 ^{b-d}	3.37 ^{a-b}	67.04 ^{d-l}	12.46 ^{bj}	0.57 ^{m-n}	0.48 ^{a-b}	0.21 ^{a-h}	0.10 ^{a-g}	0.06 ^{a-e}	18.85 ^{a-g}	68.12 ^{f-k}	13.03 ^{b-j}
Lechín de Sevilla	0.02 ^{a-d}	15.52 ^{a-l}	1.33 ^{c-k}	0.20 ^a	0.40 ^a	1.85 ^{m-t}	63.56 ^{h-l}	15.48 ^{a-g}	0.98 ^{a-h}	0.33 ^{d-l}	0.23 ^{a-g}	0.07 ^{i-m}	0.04 ^{e-f}	18.03 ^{a-h}	65.51 ^{g-k}	16.45 ^{a-g}
Loaime	0.03 ^{a-d}	17.51 ^{a-h}	1.59 ^{b-o}	0.18 ^{a-b}	0.30 ^{a-b}	2.48 ^{d-l}	62.56 ^{h-l}	13.69 ^{a-i}	0.84 ^{d-l}	0.43 ^{b-g}	0.24 ^{a-g}	0.10 ^{a-h}	0.06 ^{a-e}	20.79 ^{a-b}	64.68 ^{g-k}	14.53 ^{a-i}
Manzanilla Cacereña	0.02 ^{a-d}	13.76 ^{g-o}	1.46 ^{b-j}	0.03 ^{l-o}	0.09 ^{f-j}	1.97 ^{k-s}	75.02 ^{a-e}	6.19 ^{k-o}	0.78 ^{f-m}	0.32 ^{d-l}	0.23 ^{a-f}	0.08 ^{d-m}	0.05 ^{a-f}	16.20 ^{d-i}	76.81 ^{a-d}	6.96 ^{k-o}
Manzanilla de Sevilla	0.01 ^{a-d}	15.89 ^{a-l}	1.50 ^{b-i}	0.09 ^{b-k}	0.20 ^{b-f}	2.65 ^{c-i}	65.65 ^{d-l}	12.72 ^{c-j}	0.70 ^{h-n}	0.33 ^{d-l}	0.14 ^j	0.08 ^{e-m}	0.04 ^{d-f}	19.10 ^{a-g}	67.49 ^{d-k}	13.42 ^{c-k}
Manzanilla Prieta	0.03 ^{a-d}	13.49 ^{j-o}	1.19 ^{e-m}	0.06 ^{d-n}	0.11 ^{d-h}	2.34 ^{f-n}	75.82 ^{a-c}	5.31 ^{l-o}	0.95 ^{a-h}	0.34 ^{d-k}	0.23 ^{a-g}	0.07 ^{g-m}	0.05 ^{a-f}	16.38 ^{c-i}	77.35 ^{c-f}	6.27 ^{m-o}
Mastoidis	0.01 ^{c-d}	11.93 ^{m-o}	0.91 ^{b-o}	0.10 ^{a-h}	0.20 ^{b-d}	2.63 ^{b-h}	77.15 ^{a-b}	5.93 ^o	0.53 ⁿ	0.31 ^{f-l}	0.19 ^{e-j}	0.06 ^{j-m}	0.04 ^{e-f}	15.00 ^{h-i}	78.45 ^{a-b}	6.47 ^o
Mission Moojesk	0.02 ^{a-d}	16.26 ^{a-j}	1.5 ^{b-h}	0.13 ^{a-e}	0.32 ^{a-b}	1.59 ^{s-t}	61.06 ^l	17.62 ^{a-d}	0.86 ^{c-k}	0.31 ^{f-l}	0.2 ^{b-j}	0.09 ^{d-l}	0.05 ^{b-f}	18.44 ^{a-h}	63.08 ^{h-k}	18.48 ^{a-d}
Mixani	0.01 ^{b-d}	12.53 ^{l-o}	0.41 ^o	0.11 ^{a-g}	0.17 ^{b-f}	3.05 ^{b-e}	69.75 ^{b-j}	12.64 ^{bj}	0.54 ⁿ	0.43 ^{a-d}	0.19 ^{b-j}	0.10 ^{b-j}	0.05 ^{a-f}	16.29 ^{c-i}	70.53 ^{b-i}	13.18 ^{b-j}
Mollar de Cieza	0.03 ^{a-c}	17.82 ^{a-b}	1.47 ^{b-h}	0.07 ^{b-m}	0.13 ^{c-g}	2.14 ^{g-q}	67.27 ^{f-l}	9.27 ^l	1.03 ^{a-f}	0.37 ^{b-k}	0.23 ^{a-g}	0.09 ^{c-k}	0.06 ^{a-d}	20.59 ^{a-b}	69.11 ^{f-k}	10.30 ^{f-m}
Morona	0.03 ^{a-d}	12.42 ^{n-o}	1.03 ^{b-o}	0.07 ^{c-m}	0.10 ^{f-j}	2.52 ^{c-k}	76.27 ^a	5.97 ^{m-o}	0.73 ^{k-n}	0.40 ^{b-i}	0.30 ^a	0.11 ^{a-f}	0.05 ^{a-e}	15.60 ^{h-i}	77.70 ^a	6.70 ^{n-o}
Negrillo de la Carlota	0.02 ^{a-d}	16.21 ^{a-k}	2.09 ^{a-b}	0.04 ^{l-o}	0.10 ^{e-i}	1.64 ^{r-t}	64.75 ^{g-l}	13.66 ^{a-i}	1.00 ^{a-h}	0.24 ^{l-m}	0.14 ^j	0.08 ^{e-m}	0.03 ^f	18.26 ^{a-h}	67.09 ^{f-k}	14.66 ^{a-i}
Ojo de Liebre	0.03 ^{a-d}	14.63 ^{b-o}	1.31 ^{k-k}	0.06 ^{d-m}	0.09 ^{f-j}	3.09 ^{b-d}	71.39 ^{a-i}	7.75 ^o	0.93 ^{a-j}	0.41 ^{b-h}	0.18 ^{g-j}	0.08 ^{d-l}	0.05 ^{a-f}	18.35 ^{a-h}	72.97 ^{a-h}	8.68 ^{h-o}
Pendolino	0.01 ^{c-d}	16.09 ^{a-k}	1.05 ^{g-n}	0.03 ^{n-o}	0.05 ^{j-i}	1.53 ^t	70.35 ^{b-j}	9.33 ^l	1.06 ^{a-f}	0.21 ^m	0.19 ^{b-j}	0.05 ^m	0.04 ^{e-f}	17.97 ^{a-i}	71.64 ^{b-i}	10.39 ^{g-m}
Picual	0.03 ^{a-d}	14.99 ^{b-n}	1.64 ^{a-g}	0.07 ^{c-m}	0.10 ^{f-j}	2.64 ^{b-h}	75.08 ^{a-e}	3.91 ^o	0.82 ^{d-l}	0.37 ^{b-k}	0.21 ^{a-j}	0.09 ^{d-k}	0.05 ^{a-f}	18.24 ^{a-h}	77.03 ^{c-c}	4.73 ^o
Picual de Almería	0.02 ^{b-d}	11.7 ^o	0.55 ^o	0.05 ^{l-o}	0.05 ^{h-j}	3.30 ^{a-c}	75.52 ^{d-d}	7.23 ^o	0.67 ^{j-n}	0.47 ^{a-c}	0.27 ^{a-d}	0.11 ^{a-f}	0.05 ^{a-e}	15.70 ^{g-i}	76.40 ^{a-e}	7.90 ^o
Picudo	0.02 ^{a-d}	18.19 ^{a-c}	2.39 ^a	0.06 ^{g-o}	0.12 ^{d-g}	1.61 ^{s-t}	57.12 ^l	18.74 ^{a-b}	1.15 ^{a-d}	0.32 ^{e-l}	0.16 ^{g-j}	0.08 ^{d-m}	0.05 ^{b-f}	20.33 ^{a-b}	59.78 ^{h-k}	19.89 ^{a-b}
Plementa Bjelica	0.02 ^{a-d}	14.52 ^{c-o}	1.19 ^{g-m}	0.07 ^{b-m}	0.09 ^{g-j}	4.16 ^a	69.02 ^{b-j}	9.27 ^l	0.61 ^{l-n}	0.60 ^a	0.24 ^{a-f}	0.13 ^{a-b}	0.07 ^a	19.58 ^{a-e}	70.53 ^{b-i}	9.98 ^m
Royal de Cazorla	0.03 ^a	14.00 ^{e-o}	1.24 ^{e-l}	0.06 ^{e-n}	0.09 ^{f-j}	1.78 ^{p-t}	69.86 ^{b-j}	10.86 ^{f-k}	1.39 ^a	0.30 ^{j-m}	0.28 ^{a-c}	0.07 ^{h-m}	0.05 ^{a-f}	16.20 ^{d-i}	71.46 ^{b-i}	12.24 ^{d-l}
Sabatera	0.02 ^{a-d}	15.87 ^{a-l}	1.51 ^{b-i}	0.05 ^{e-o}	0.08 ^{g-j}	2.40 ^{e-m}	64.75 ^{h-l}	13.83 ^{a-h}	0.90 ^{c-k}	0.33 ^{d-l}	0.14 ^{b-j}	0.08 ^{d-m}	0.04 ^{e-f}	18.70 ^{a-g}	66.47 ^{f-k}	14.73 ^{a-i}
Sikitita	0.03 ^{a-b}	17.88 ^{a-d}	1.98 ^{a-d}	0.06 ^{f-n}	0.09 ^{f-j}	1.68 ^{q-t}	63.99 ^{h-l}	12.63 ^{bj}	0.91 ^{b-k}	0.36 ^{b-k}	0.24 ^{a-f}	0.10 ^{b-i}	0.06 ^{a-d}	20.16 ^{a-d}	66.29 ^{f-k}	13.54 ^{a-j}
Ulliri i Bardhe i Tiranes	0.01 ^{b-d}	13.19 ^o	1.19 ^{e-m}	0.02 ^o	0.06 ^j	2.65 ^{b-g}	68.41 ^{c-j}	13.12 ^{a-i}	0.75 ^{f-m}	0.33 ^{d-l}	0.16 ^{f-j}	0.07 ^{g-m}	0.04 ^{e-f}	16.3 ⁱ	69.82 ^{c-j}	13.86 ^{a-i}
Villalonga	0.03 ^{a-b}	17.61 ^{a-f}	1.55 ^{a-g}	0.15 ^{a-c}	0.25 ^{a-b}	2.00 ^{h-l}	64.17 ^{a-i}	13.44 ^{a-i}	0.96 ^{a-h}	0.36 ^{b-k}	0.24 ^{a-g}	0.10 ^{a-i}	0.06 ^{a-e}	19.6 ^{c-c}	65.24 ^{g-k}	14.15 ^{a-i}

Fig. 1. Variability expressed as standard deviation (%) in the concentration of palmitic acid, oleic acid, and linoleic acid of VOOs obtained from 45 cultivars in three consecutive crop seasons.

Fig. 2. Percentage of variability in the concentration of fatty acids in VOOs explained by cultivar, crop season, and interaction effect by ANOVA analysis.

cultivars set. Thus, a significant negative correlation was observed between MUFAs *versus* PUFAs ($R = -0.942$; p -value < 0.0001) and MUFAs *versus* SFAs ($R = -0.774$; p -value < 0.0001), while a positive correlation was found between PUFAs and SFAs ($R = 0.574$; p -value < 0.0001).

The classification of cultivars by HCA and PCA was based on the fatty acids profile of VOOs using the mean concentrations. The stability of this classification was evaluated by Discriminant Analysis using the data of the three crop seasons (45 cultivars \times 3 crop seasons = 135 samples). Discriminant Analysis confirmed that 75.9% of the samples were reclassified in the same groups previously established (Table S4). The misclassified samples support the relevance of the interannual factor to explain the variability in the fatty acids profile of VOOs. Thus, VOO

samples from some cultivars experienced quantitative changes in the relative content of the main fatty acids that altered the assignment.

3.3. Influence of the cultivar \times crop season effect on the fatty acids profile of virgin olive oil

As previously mentioned, the cultivar \times crop season factor contributed to explain partially the variability in the content of VOO fatty acids. The ANOVA test showed that the interaction factor explained 24, 25 and 22% of the variability measured for SFAs, MUFAs and PUFAs, respectively (Fig. 2). Therefore, the cultivar \times crop season factor should be considered, which means that not all cultivars followed the same

Fig. 3. Statistical analysis for discrimination of cultivars according to the fatty acids profile of VOO in: high relative content in MUFAs and moderate content in SFAs/PUFAs (blue, Group 1, G1), moderate relative content in MUFAs and high content in SFAs/PUFAs (red, Group 2, G2). (A) Hierarchical Cluster Analysis. (B) PCA biplot. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

variability trend in the three monitored seasons. This was also demonstrated by the Discriminant Analysis since 24.1% of the VOO samples were misclassified according to their fatty acids profile (Table S4).

We evaluated the variability trends of SFAs, MUFAs and PUFAs in the cultivars set along the three crop seasons. This analysis allowed dividing the cultivars in two groups according to the concentration variations in the three seasons. We detected in most cultivars a significant increase (p -value < 0.005, mean value of 5%) in the concentration of SFAs and

PUFAs in the third crop season. The contrary pattern was observed for MUFAs that were significantly increased (p -value < 0.005) ca. 8% in these cultivars in the same crop season.

On the contrary side, the other group of cultivars experienced a significant increase (p -value < 0.005) in SFAs and PUFAs in the second crop season, with a mean value of 2%. For the same group, MUFAs were significantly reduced by 4% in the same season. Thus, concentrations in SFAs, PUFAs and MUFAs seem to follow variable trends in the three

Fig. 4. Variability trends in the concentration of SFAs, MUFAs and PUFAs along the three monitored crop seasons. Results are shown for the top-5 cultivars experiencing the greatest alterations in the second and third crop season.

monitored seasons. These trends can be visualized in Fig. 4 for the top-5 cultivars of each group that experienced the highest concentration changes in the three families of fatty acids.

3.4. Variability in fatty acids profile of VOO according to climatic conditions

In an additional study, we compared the average relative contents of SFAs, PUFAs and MUFAs considering the 45 cultivars in the three crop seasons (Fig. 5). In this case, the three groups of fatty acids did not report significant differences when contents in the first and second crop seasons were compared. However, the third crop season revealed significant differences for SFAs, MUFAs and PUFAs (p -value < 0.05). Thus, in the third crop season cultivars increased the content in SFAs and PUFAs, while MUFAs were significantly decreased. We tried to correlate these variations with climatic parameters such as average temperature, total annual rainfall, and accumulated precipitation from June to October, that fit the period when the development of olive fruits takes place (Rallo et al., 2018) (Fig. S1). Minimum differences were detected in average temperatures in the 2015, 2016 and 2017 seasons. However, accumulated precipitation in the June–October period was clearly lower in 2017 (64.5 mm in 2017 versus 119 and 183 mm in 2015 and 2016, respectively). This variation was also reflected in the fruit moisture expressed in percentage, which was significantly lower (p -value < 0.05) in 2017 as compared to the two previous crop seasons (Fig. S2). Nevertheless, no significant differences were found in oil extraction yield expressed as dry matter percentage.

In a previous study with the same set of VOO samples, we found an increase in the phenolic content in VOOs produced in 2017, which was associated to stress conditions in the summer period (Miho et al., 2021). Concerning fatty acids, we found a general decrease in MUFAs in VOOs produced in 2017 associated to an increase in SFAs/PUFAs. Our results were in line with those provided by Orlandi et al., who evaluated the water stress on three Italian cultivars in 12 consecutive seasons. The

authors associated a water stress with a decrease of oleic acid content and with an increase in the levels of linoleic and linolenic acids (Orlandi, Bonofiglio, Romano, & Fornaciari, 2012). On the other hand, Romero et al. found an opposite pattern in a study developed during four seasons with a unique cultivar: Arbequina. Particularly, they observed that the MUFAs content was decreased when the accumulated precipitation increased in the fruit ripening period (Romero, Tovar, Ramo, & Motilva, 2003). This trend could be explained by the contribution of temperature variations to stress. Thus, in the study reported by Romero et al. (2003) yearly maximum temperature was below 35 °C in summer, while in our study maximum temperatures were around 40 °C in the same period (Fig. S1). Nissim et al. (2020) evaluated the effect of maximum temperature in the May–November period in the quality of olive oil by comparing two areas with maximum temperatures above 40 °C and below 35 °C. In two consecutive crop seasons, the concentration of oleic acid was significantly lower in olive oil from five cultivars (Barnea, Koroneiki, Coratina, Picholine and Sour) in the area with maximum temperature stress (Nissim et al., 2020). Therefore, considering our results and previous studies, reduced accumulated precipitation during fruit development accompanied by high temperature promotes the reduction of MUFAs and the increase of SFAs and PUFAs.

As previously mentioned, some cultivars reported concentrations of some fatty acids outside the required limits reported by the International Olive Council (IOC, 2019) (Table S1). Thus, ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’, ‘Picudo’ and ‘Blanqueta’ presented C18:1 level below the required minimum concentration in the 2017 crop season, which corresponds to the year with the lowest accumulated precipitation within the June–October period. The opposite situation occurred with ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’, ‘Blanqueta’ and ‘Gordal de Granada’, which reported C18:2 relative concentrations above the limit established by the International Olive Council in the same crop season. Therefore, these variations affect the relative contents of main fatty acids, which can influence quality grade for some cultivars.

Fig. 5. Mean concentrations of SFAs, MUFAs and PUFAs in the set of 45 cultivars in the three monitored seasons. Different letters express significant changes (p -value < 0.05) for each group of fatty acids by comparing the three seasons.

4. Conclusions

The three years of study revealed that the fatty acids profile of VOO differed significantly among the olive cultivars. This variability was attributed to the cultivar and the cultivar × crop season interaction. The cultivar factor explained the biggest proportion of total variability (56%), while the interaction effect explained around 25%. The crop season factor explained only the 10% of variability. Thus, the cultivar is the main factor supporting the variability in the content of PUFAs and MUFAs, which are directly associated to the health benefits of olive oil.

Furthermore, the extended set of 71 cultivars analyzed in this study was clustered on the basis of their fatty acids' composition: (1) high MUFAs content and moderate SFAs/PUFAs content, and (2) moderate MUFAs content and high SFAs/PUFAs content. On the other hand, the results of this study show that reduced accumulated precipitation during fruit development contributed to the decline of oleic acid concentration, which could affect the nutritional properties of monovarietal oils.

These results complete those provided by previous studies focused on phenolic compounds to give rise to future olive breeding programs to obtain olive oils with the desired phenolic and fatty acids profiles. Both families of compounds are responsible of the healthy properties and oxidative stability of VOOs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

S. Tomé-Rodríguez: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **F. Barba-Palomeque:** Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Validation. **C.A. Ledesma-Escobar:** Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **H. Miho:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Resources. **C. M. Díez:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition. **F. Priego-Capote:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded jointly by: the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (PID2019-111373RB-I00 project), the European Unions Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Gen4Olive, grant agreement 101000427), and the European Regional Development Fund/European Social Fund (“Investing in your future”). Consortium for Biomedical Research in Frailty and Healthy Ageing (CIBERFES) is an initiative of Carlos III Institute of Health. Funding for open access charge was supported by University of Cordoba.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2023.136175>.

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